

IRL-DataSpace & IRL-DSSC

A Brief

A Common Data Space & Support Centre for Ireland

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R&I activities are increasingly data-driven and address global challenges to inform better public policy-making across different disciplines – societal, environmental and economical.

A robust, federated and efficient national data ecosystem is critical to achieve the objectives and relevant impacts envisioned in key national and relevant European strategies.

*Impact 2030: Ireland’s Research and Innovation Strategy
National AI Strategy for Ireland
Climate Action Plan for Ireland
Open Data Strategy 2023-2027
National Action Plan for Open Research 2020-2030
National Smart Specialisation Strategy for Innovation
European Data Strategy (European Data Act, European Data Governance Act)*

IRL-DataSpace and IRL-DSSC are an essential component for Ireland to deliver these key national and European strategies.

 Currently, the Irish data ecosystem is complex, varied, fragmented and disparate, with several siloed data systems, providers and holders. The status quo imparts a high entry barrier on researchers and users, and significantly diminishes their efficiency. Inherently, this severely limits multi- and inter-disciplinary cross-institutional collaborative R&I among academia, public sector and industry. This is because of the ineffective use and limitations in extracting value from the data (open and closed) from different stakeholders through technical systems, tools and practices that are truly FAIR-compliant.

Implemented as

- ❖ Project-specific or institutional systems
- ❖ Database
Collection for storage, access & retrieval
- ❖ Data warehouse
Copied & provisioned for analytical use

Examples include

- ❖ Thematic Data Spaces
- ❖ ESGF node (Earth Systems Grid Federation)
- ❖ EODC (Earth Observation Data Cube)
- ❖ EOSC node (European Open Science Cloud)
- ❖ GAIA-X node
- ❖ ...
- ❖ Bespoke implementation

Data ecosystem in Ireland is complex & varied

- Some institutions/domains have mature data systems (enabling high FAIR-ness), while others have basic data systems (low ability to enable FAIR-ness).
- Ireland’s ecosystem of diverse data systems will need to be unified as a federated system of systems based on FAIR principles, practices and technologies.
- Data sharing cannot be through a centralised solution within a single storage infrastructure due to inherent requirements of data ownership, governance, sensitivity and security.
- Data has gravity. Consequently, copying/moving data between different systems for inter-/multi-disciplinary and/or cross-institutional R&I is expensive, inefficient and not scalable.

Data has a lifecycle

- Data in the research, public sector and enterprise communities has a lifecycle. It progresses through various stages of maturity, quality, publication-readiness and preservation.
- It is essential that institutions, sectoral communities and national-level organisations coordinate, robustly manage and govern datasets to mature them to open and FAIR Data.

Data ecosystem limitations and challenges have to be overcome collectively at a national-level when working towards the global challenges (societal, environmental and economic) that are prioritised in key national and European strategies and that rely on multi-/inter-disciplinary and cross-institutional collaborative R&I among academia, public sector and industry.

To overcome these limitations and challenges, it is essential to build IRL-DataSpace (the Common Data Space for Ireland) through which to synergise and unify existing data-related ecosystem stakeholders and resources.

Build a Common Data Space for Ireland (IRL-DataSpace) with a Support Centre (IRL-DSSC)

- IRL-DataSpace will serve as a national-level single point of entry to R&I-relevant FAIR data (open and closed) for all R&I-focused users, projects and activities.
- IRL-DataSpace will federate Ireland’s R&I-related data systems, owners and providers at technical and governance levels compliant with national, European and institutional requirements and policies.
- IRL-DSSC will fill the existing gap by providing trusted neutral national-level technical coordination and support to bridge data system operators, data governors, R&I activities, relevant FAIR data programmes, funders and policy-makers.
- IRL-DataSpace and IRL-DSSC together will collectively increase, accelerate and align the maturity and FAIR-ness of data systems and datasets across Ireland that are relevant and essential for R&I activities at institutional, domain, national and regional levels.
- It is proposed that the IRL-DSSC be co-led by ICHEC and HEAnet as national providers of digital infrastructures and services across networking, compute and data technologies.

ICHEC and HEAnet share the vision to expedite establishment of a national-level Data Space Support Centre for Ireland (IRL-DSSC) to engage stakeholders across the community for their participation and co-development.

The IRL-DSSC will play a pivotal role in advancing the current national data ecosystem into a federated, FAIR, high-SLA and cost-effective ecosystem with robust digital platform resources, services for data sharing and governance, and a national-level professional support team. The IRL-DSSC will engage with and leverage expertise from the EU Data Spaces Support Centre.

It is proposed that IRL-DSSC be co-led by ICHEC and HEAnet as the national providers of digital infrastructures and services across computing data and networking infrastructure and technologies, with sponsorship from government departments and participation of relevant stakeholders. For this, ICHEC and HEAnet have available the expertise that can be leveraged.

Furthermore, ICHEC and HEAnet have existing resources as a part of their mandated national digital infrastructure and services which can be leveraged to implement a number of these core cross-cutting functional elements.

This framework and roadmap will deliver IRL-DataSpace by accelerating and supporting a structured synergised unification of the national data ecosystem (composed of academic and public research bodies, and enterprise organisations where relevant) which is currently disparate and fragmented. IRL-DataSpace will be a federation of data stakeholders, data systems and services at a national level that also links with relevant European resources. The beneficiary activities and exploitation of IRL-DataSpace target multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary R&I collaborations driven by academic and public bodies with industry partners as required.

*IRL-DataSpace and IRL-DSSC are crucial for R&I impact across disciplines in environment, society, economy at national and international levels, by dealing with grand challenges and informing better public policy-making. This is consistent with the Programme for Government – Our Shared Future – as highlighted in the **Impact 2030 Strategy**. IRL-DataSpace and IRL-DSSC are an essential component for Ireland to deliver these key national and European strategies.*

To R&I activities conducted by institutions, research centres, projects or researchers, we highlight that it is

essential to coordinate, robustly manage and govern datasets to mature them to open and FAIR Data, facilitated by the IRL-DSSC (Common Data Space Support Centre for Ireland).

To data systems operators, data holders and governors, we call out for their participation to mature the FAIR-

ness of their systems and data in a national-level federation based on standardised and FAIR technologies and practices. The IRL-Data Space (Common Data Space for Ireland) is the solution for federation coordinated by the IRL-DSSC (Common Data Space Support Centre for Ireland).

To policy-makers and funders, we emphasise that

- Ireland's ecosystem of diverse data systems will need to be unified as a federated system of systems based on FAIR principles, practices and technologies. This requires incentivisation for the participant R&I activities, data systems operators and data holders to engage.
- Building the IRL-DataSpace (Common Data Space for Ireland) will federate Ireland's R&I-related data systems, owners and providers at technical and governance levels in compliance with national, EU, institution-/activity-specific requirements and policies.
- Establishing the IRL-DSSC (Common Data Space Support Centre for Ireland) would lead the development of IRL-DataSpace collaboratively with data system operators, data holders, governors and R&I activities. The IRL-DSSC will fill the existing gap by providing trusted neutral national-level technical coordination and support to bridge data system operators, data governors, R&I activities, relevant FAIR data programmes, funders and policy-makers.

IRL-DataSpace complements the vision for European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Ireland outlined by HEAnet in consultation with ICHEC and the consortium of Irish Research Libraries (IREL). These are aligned and linked to enable the connection of Data Spaces to EOSC.

The 2024-2027 roadmap (see overleaf) to build the IRL-DataSpace supported by the IRL-DSSC, its working groups and all relevant stakeholders includes

- briefings and consultations to onboard all stakeholders,
- focused white papers to establish technical specifications for IRL-DataSpace, requirements for different R&I disciplines, and all-island joint activities,
- the finalisation and support required from policy-makers and funders, and
- development and operationalising IRL-DataSpace as a National Service by 2027.

